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FEMALE LEADERSHIP, PERFORMANCE, AND GOVERNANCE IN MICROFINANCE INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the relations between female leadership, firm performance, and corporate governance in a global panel of 329 Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) in 73 countries covering the years 1998 to 2008. The microfinance industry is particularly suited for studying the impact of female leadership on governance and performance because of its mission orientation, its entrepreneurial nature, diverse institutional conditions, and high percentage of female leaders. We find female leadership to be significantly associated with larger boards, younger firms, a non-commercial legal status, and more female clientele. Furthermore, we find that a female chief executive officer and a female chairman of the board are positively related to MFI performance, but this result is not driven by improved governance.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The microfinance institution's (MFI) purpose or mission is to provide access to financial services to poor families and small businesses situated mostly in developing and newly industrialized countries. Microfinance is to a large extent a women's business. Female borrowers are the MFIs' largest market, and lending to women is considered one of the main reasons for microfinance's success (Armendáriz and Morduch, 2010). But microfinance is not only a business *for* women it is to a large extent also a business *by* women. Interestingly, beside Nobel laureate Muhammad Yunus, several women are industry icons: for example, Pilar Ramirez of Banco FIE in Bolivia and Ingrid Munro in Jamii Bora in Kenya. The female proportion of top executives and directors in MFIs is high. In our sample the CEO is female in 27% of MFIs, the chair is female in 23%, and 29% of all board seats are held by women. These proportions are much higher than corresponding figures in traditional firms. For instance, for their very large sample of U.S. companies, Adams and Ferreira (2009) report that only 8.8% of directors are female. In this paper, we investigate whether female leadership improves governance and financial performance in MFIs.

Unlike studies in high-income countries (Schrader et al., 1997; Smith et al. 2006; Adams and Ferreira, 2009) that often consider only the role of directors, we address these questions for the chief executive officer (CEO), the chair, as well as board directors. Moreover, our study is novel because it surveys entrepreneurial firms (MFIs) in emerging markets. Our data tells us that the MFIs' median time in operation is eight years. In eight years, the weight of tradition has not settled in a firm, so that a masculine culture has not yet become ingrained, and the male network has not had time to become established. Thus, the "glass ceiling" (Kanter, 1977) between men at the top and women in jobs below has not had time to set. This creates opportunities for able women to rise in the MFI's leadership hierarchy. Microfinance is also typically a mission-driven organization (Randøy et al., 2014). Thus, we are able to tell if the

leadership's gender matters for governance and performance in circumstances that are different from those usually studied.

The female orientation is often a stated goal in many MFIs. The MFIs in our sample have indicated whether they prefer to lend to women. 44% state that they have such a female bias. This female attention is evident in supporting international organizations for microfinance as well. The objective of the Microcredit Summit Campaign, which plays a central role in the promotion of microfinance, is “to ensure that 175 million of the world’s poorest families, **especially women**, receive credit for self-employment and other financial and business services” [our emphasis] (www.microcreditsummit.org).

When many MFIs are gender biased, it becomes interesting to study how well female leaders perform. Does a woman bring better governance and better financial performance to the MFIs they run? Mersland and Strøm (2009) argue that because a female CEO is better able to tap into the local, often female information network, female leaders may design product and procedures that better meet the female users' needs. We follow this line of argument here, and extend the analysis to the chair and the board of directors. Our main hypothesis is that female leadership has beneficial consequences for the MFI's governance as well as its financial performance. In gender biased MFIs, female leaders could be better matched to the challenges and opportunities that female customers face.

But female leadership is possibly endogenous, that is, specific MFIs may attract female leaders. If these are also good performers, we cannot attribute good financial performance to female leadership. At most we can state there is a correlation. We attempt to disentangle the reverse causality problem by following the Heckman (1979) dummy endogenous variable method. We also test for sample selectivity bias by the inverse Mill's ratio test.

The research on female leadership is scant in microfinance. Armendáriz and Morduch (2010) argue that female targeting and financial sustainability are perfectly compatible, since female targeting within microfinance has often been attributed to increased efficiency due to higher repayment rates among female borrowers. D'Espallier et al. (2011) confirm that the targeting of women leads to higher repayment rates in MFIs. Both deal with the customer aspect. However, our study investigates whether female leadership has an impact upon the MFI's governance and its financial performance in an industry that to a large extent caters to female customers.

In the general governance literature, only Adams and Ferreira (2009) address both the governance and performance issues related to female management, but limit the study to directors. They find that female directors are “tougher” monitors than men, but also that a positive effect of female directors on performance is only detectable for firms with weak governance structures when instrumental variables (IV) methodology is employed. Furthermore, Schrader et al. (1997), Smith et al. (2006), and Francoeur et al. (2008) investigate the relationships between a female CEO and female directors on the one hand and financial performance on the other. These studies do not look into corporate governance issues. All studies cited here use data from diverse industries in Western countries. In contrast, we investigate the effects of three leadership types (CEO, Chair and Directors) upon both corporate governance and financial performance in an homogeneous industry in many developing countries.

The sample consists of 329 MFIs in 73 countries from 1998 to 2008. The data are from rating agencies and cover up to six years of data per individual MFI. The sample is drawn from the same industry, where MFIs largely follow the same mode of operation, focusing on loans to poor people and small enterprises, granting small loans with a short maturity, and demanding frequent repayments (Helms, 2006). Borrowers often have little or no collateral or credit

history. Frequent repayments enable the MFI to quickly assess the borrower's repayment ability. Nevertheless, heterogeneity may arise due to different firm and country characteristics, in particular attitudes to women. We control for heterogeneity by firm and country background variables. Firm controls include the MFI's business practice, differences in institutional background, and commonly used controls such as MFI size, age, and risk. The country controls encompass a set of country variables, and also include world regional dummies. It turns out that despite cultural diversity, the fraction of female leadership positions is remarkably similar across countries. By controlling for country differences, our findings are relevant for corporate governance in other than emerging markets (Aguilera and Jackson, 2010).

We find that female leadership is negatively related to such governance measures as the number of board meetings, internal audits, and the separation of the CEO's and chair's roles, but positively related to MFI financial performance. This is contrary to what Adams and Ferreira (2009) find for female directors. Thus, the quality of an MFI's CEO and chair seems to be more important for the MFI's success than general corporate governance. Country specific variables complement these findings, as they are correlated with corporate governance but not financial performance. The results are robust to variations in estimating methodology, variable definition, and regression specification.

This article proceeds as follows. Section 2 develops hypotheses from former literature on female top executives' and board members' influence on firm performance and corporate governance. Section 3 gives a brief introduction to the microfinance industry and its special focus on women together with data descriptives. Section 4 lays out the estimating methodologies and also defines variables. Section 5 covers the conditions under which female leadership tends to arise, and Section 6 examines the relations between female leadership and corporate governance. Section 7 deals with the relations between female leadership and the

MFI's financial performance. In section 8 we perform a number of robustness checks, and section 9 presents our conclusions.

2. GENDER, GOVERNANCE AND PERFORMANCE

Mersland and Strøm (2009) find that a female CEO induces a higher financial performance in the MFI. They assume this is due to the female CEO's better understanding of the market in which the MFI operates. This is a matching, or sorting, argument implying that an MFI that is matched with a leadership that has the same traits will perform better. In this case, the "same traits" refers to gender, so that for instance an MFI favoring female clients is matched with female leadership. The underlying theory for this is the Becker (1973) model for the marriage market¹. Thus, the hypothesis is that female managers and directors will improve the MFI's governance and financial performance due to the better match between the MFI's leadership team and its market conditions. In microfinance, Ghatak (2000) shows how the Becker model may be applied to the matching of good borrowers in a group lending scheme. In Thomas and Ramaswamy (1996) the matching of leaders with specific traits and the firm's strategy increases firm performance.

The matching hypothesis of female leadership and the MFI contains two sub-hypotheses. The first is that female leadership is more likely to be found in MFIs with a bias towards female customers. The second is that an MFI's governance and financial performance improves with female managers and directors. But we hereby encounter two potential endogeneity problems. The first is the reverse causality case (Hermalin and Weisbach, 1998) when the MFI performing financially well attracts a female CEO. We control for reverse causation of female leadership in financial performance regressions by the Heckman (1979) model for an

¹ Becker gives various examples of matching: "...the optimal sorting of more able workers and more able firms, more "modern" farms and more able farmers, or more informed customers and more honest shopkeepers".

endogenous dummy variable. The second endogeneity problem is sample selectivity, that is, the selection of a female CEO, chair or director might be related to the emphasized focus on female customers i.e. MFIs hire a female leader because most clients are women, not because of their qualifications. We handle this second endogeneity problem by the inverse Mill's ratio (IMR) test. In the gender literature, the Kanter (1977) "window-dressing" or "tokenism" is an argument for the endogeneity of female leadership. She proposes that a company's election of female directors is done in order to demonstrate commitment to gender-neutral policies.

The dominant approach in gender studies seems to be that both governance and financial performance improves with more women in management and board. Teigen (2000) puts the positive gender effect down to what may be called the *underused resource effect* and the *underused diversity resource effect*. The total resource pool of equally able men and women is underused when candidates for management and director positions are pulled from the sub-set of men only. The underused diversity resource means that managers and directors are not optimally matched to the conditions of their firm. This last effect could be especially important in microfinance, where the majority of clients are female. Female leaders should therefore increase governance quality and financial performance in MFIs. Beneficial leadership is often seen as an intrinsic quality among women. Thus, Shrader et al. (1997) summarize this in an early investigation: "There is evidence that women are more oriented toward supporting and maintaining relationships than men. ... Therefore, as more and more women assume managerial positions, organizational learning, climate, and performance should improve." Bertrand and Schoar (2003) conjecture that female managers and directors represent a new management style. If this is true, it should only increase the effects on governance and performance. In particular, in the Adams and Ferreira (2007) model directors perform two functions, monitoring and advice. Thus, female directors could be better advisors

to the CEO than male. This could be especially important in the young and entrepreneurial MFIs, where growth rates are unusually high.

It appears that most empirical investigations start from the resource effects, but that the advantages of matching go unnoticed. Furthermore, only Adams and Ferreira (2009) address governance and financial performance, although predictions are for both issues. They find that women on the board generate better governance, but better firm performance follows only in firms with weak overall governance. Moreover, besides the above-mentioned Shrader et al. (1997) study, we are aware of only Smith et al. (2006) and Francoeur et al. (2007) who study different management and director positions. These find that female managers (e.g. the female CEO) improves firm performance, but that female directors are only weakly or negatively linked to financial performance. Besides this, some studies investigate the role of gender in the top management team. Welbourne et al. (2007) find that short-term and long-term financial performance (Tobin's Q) improves when women are part of the top management teams in firms undertaking an initial public offering (IPO).

By far the most numerous studies concern the relationship between female directors and financial performance. This has been addressed in cross-sectional and panel data studies, in event studies using time series, and in a natural experiment setting. First, cross-sectional and panel data studies show conflicting results. Some studies find a positive relation (Carter et al., 2003; Campbell and Minguez-Vera, 2008), while others detect a negative relation (Shrader et al., 1997; Smith et al., 2006; Rose, 2008; Adams and Ferreira, 2009; Bøhren and Strøm, 2010; Carter et al., 2010; Gallego-Álvarez et al., 2010). Second, the event studies measure stock price reaction to the announcement of a female director. Here, the results lean towards a positive relationship. Farrell and Hersch (2005) report no wealth effect, while Campbell and Minguez-Vera (2010) and Kang et al. (2010) find positive reactions. Third, Ahern and Dittmar (2012) utilize the natural experiment setting that the quota regulation in Norway from

2003 to 2008 affords, and find a negative relationship. Thus, different methodological approaches yield conflicting results, both within methodological approach and between approaches.

Can conflicting results be due to the measures used? For instance, Konrad et al. (2008) forward the “critical mass” hypothesis that at least three women must be on a board for their female advantages to be realized. The female director effect is possibly most evident in board committees (Carter et al., 2010). We are able to test the first possibility, but lack information about the second. Furthermore, it is difficult to accept psychological explanations for superior female leadership. In fact, the Alvesson and Billing (2009) comprehensive survey of the psychological literature on management style reveals no large differences along gender lines.

The conflicting results may also stem from different institutional and country heterogeneity (Aguilera and Jackson, 2010). La Porta et al. (1998) underline differences in law traditions in common law and Roman (Civil) law countries. Terjesen and Singh (2008) find cross-country differences in the fraction of female directors using a 43 country sample. Furthermore, a robust result in the general board literature is that the more complex the firm is in terms of the size and span of its operations, the more outside directors are recruited (Baker and Gompers, 2003; Boone et al., 2007; Linck et al., 2008). Speckbacher (2008) argues that since nonprofit firms often have complex objectives, they will typically have larger boards. Thus, we include a number of institutional and country controls for the regressions.

3. WOMEN IN MICROFINANCE: DATA AND VARIABLE DEFINITIONS

The microfinance mission is to provide low-income families and small businesses access to financial services. MFIs have a double objective, to serve the poor and to do so in a financially sustainable way (Morduch, 1999). Starting as experimental development schemes

in Asia and Latin America in the 1970s, microfinance has become a major industry today. More than 3,000 MFIs report their numbers to the Microcredit Summit (www.microcreditsummit.org), and they provide more than 150 million people with credit. More than 100 international funds invest in microfinance offering equity, loans, bonds, and collateralized debt obligations (www.mixmarket.org). The industry is young and entrepreneurial, in fact, the median age is 8 years in our sample, 25% are under banking authorities regulation, and the incorporation ranges from shareholder ownership (25%) to cooperatives (16%) and non-governmental organizations (52%).

Our data set is based on rating assessment reports gathered by specialized rating agencies and encompasses 329 MFIs operating in 73 different countries worldwide in the years 1998-2008.

². At each rating, the raters collect data for the rating year and years immediately preceding. In this way, up to six years of data for an MFI are available for the period 1998 to 2008. The amount of detail varies in the reports, resulting in different numbers of observations. No dataset is perfectly representative of the microfinance field. In particular, our dataset contains relatively few megasized MFIs, and does not cover the virtually endless numbers of small savings and credit cooperatives. The former are rated by such agencies as Moody's and Standard & Poor's, while the latter are not rated at all. Ratings data are, however, considered among the most representative available for the microfinance industry (Mersland and Strøm, 2009).

Information in the rating reports are collected during on-site visits to the MFI by specialized evaluators working in the rating agencies. The information is thus not self-reported by the

² The dataset consists of rating reports from five rating agencies: MicroRate, Microfinanza, Planet Rating, Crisil, and M-Cril. It is an updated version of the dataset used by Mersland and Strøm (2009) and variables on gender leadership have been included. At the time of collecting the data the rating agencies were supported by the rating Fund of The Consultative Group to Assist the Poor (CGAP) and the Interamerican Development Bank (IDB) and the reports were made publically available at the World Wide Web. The donor support has now shrunk and the public availability policy has changed. Some examples of reports are, however, still available at www.ratinginitiative.org and www.ratingfund2.org or at the websites of the rating agencies.

MFI but is collected by the evaluator and further screened by the rating committee at the rating agency's main office. The information in rating reports is therefore regarded to be of high quality, and rating of MFIs is one of the main transparency initiatives in the microfinance industry (Beisland, Mersland and Randøy, 2014). The MFI rating assessments are much wider than traditional credit ratings, as they aim to measure the MFIs' ability to reach their multiple sets of objectives (Beisland and Mersland, 2012). The purpose of rating reports is to present independent information that stakeholders, such as lenders, donors, owners or managers, can use to make informed decisions. Even if a rating agency argues that its methodology is different from that of other agencies, the core information used in this study consists of standard indicators that are calculated similarly across the industry and by all rating agencies.

Table 1 provides a detailed description of the main variables used in our analyses, as well as a number of summary statistics. The table contains definitions of female leadership, financial performance, and governance, the set of MFI and country control variables, and social mission and institutional variables that enter as instruments.

Table 1

Female leadership. The table shows the measures for the three female leadership³ categories, CEO, chair, and director. The female director is defined in four different ways in order to accommodate for potential variations in results when definitions change (Adams and Ferreira, 2009; Carter et al., 2010), and for the Konrad et al. (2008) critical mass of at least three female directors measure. Consequently, we use the indicator variable as the main female director definition, and try the other three in robustness checks. In some cases it has been impossible to ascertain the fraction of female directors. When information on the number of

³ For most MFIs, the female leadership variables have been collected only once, namely in the year in which the assessment by the rating agency was done. When this is the case, we assume female leadership variables to be constant over the years in which other time-varying information is available.

female directors is missing, we often know the gender of the chair, in which case we are able to construct a binary variable showing whether women are on the board or not. Both the female director fraction and the binary for female director are used in our regressions.

Corporate governance. We choose the number of board meetings, CEO/Chair duality, internal auditors, and board size as governance mechanisms⁴. The number of board meetings measures the intensity of the board's work, and thus, the more meetings, the higher is the monitoring function. The variable may be a relevant measure of monitoring intensity in the fast-growing microfinance industry. The number of board meetings is close to eight on average with a median of four. This is fewer than Monks and Minow (2008) report, but then MFIs do often not have sub-committees. Entrepreneurial firms often combine the CEO and chair functions. However, governance recommendations (Cadbury, 2002; Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2004) warn against such power concentration. CEO/Chair duality is therefore an indication of less monitoring. An internal audit linked to the board can give the board independent information on goal fulfillment. An internal auditor means more monitoring. The overview of the literature on audit fees by Hay et al. (2006) shows that fees are related to the firm's size, complexity, governance, and independence. The CEO/Chair duality and internal auditor fractions are both low on average. The average board size of seven members (median six) seems to be on par with international experience. Board size has turned out to be hard to categorize. Early studies in Yermack (1996) and Eisenberg et al. (1998) find a negative relation between board size and firm performance. Adams and Ferreira (2009) and Mersland and Strøm (2009) confirm the negative sign. A possible explanation is that firms lose business opportunities due to longer decision time in larger boards. However, studies of endogeneity of governance mechanisms (Baker and Gompers,

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2003; Boone et al., 2007; Linck et al., 2008) find that board size tends to vary with the firm's size and complexity. Therefore, the sign is hard to predict. Furthermore, we note the large dispersion in the data on the number of board meetings and board size. In a young industry experiments with the best governance setup are to be expected. Adams and Ferreira (2009) use board attendance and CEO turnover as measures of governance quality. We believe our proxies more directly measure relevant governance issues in microfinance. Thus, we expect that board meetings, internal audit, and board size increases with female leadership, and that the CEO/Chair duality is less prevalent with female leadership.

Financial performance. We use return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE) as financial performance measures together with operational and financial self-sufficiency (OSS and FSS, respectively). Market performance measures are impossible since no MFI in our sample is listed. ROA, ROE, and FSS are all taken directly from the raters' reports. OSS is defined as portfolio revenues divided by operational expenses. This measure is free from bias resulting from different capital structure, access to subsidized funding and possible differences in default policies in the MFI. FSS is an adjusted measure of OSS taking into account financial costs, default costs, subsidies and other MFI specific adjustments. OSS and FSS are commonly used metrics in MFI evaluations (Armendáriz and Morduch, 2010, p. 243). Table 1 shows that, on the whole, microfinance is not a lucrative business. On average, both ROA and ROE are low and FSS is less than 1.0. We expect financial performance to increase with female leadership.

Social mission. The social mission variables encompass the MFI's gender bias, its rurality bias, and the average loan. Table 1 reveals that the average loan is USD 734 and the median is USD 351. These are often used measures of poverty outreach in the microfinance literature (Schreiner, 2002). In 44% of cases, the rating agencies attest that MFIs have a female gender bias in their lending practices. Unfortunately, many MFIs do not report their percentage of

female customers. Those who do, however, show a percentage in the 70–75% range, which is close to that reported in Cull et al. (2009). Thus, the female fraction is high in MFIs on both the customer and the leadership sides. Especially when the MFI has a gender bias, it is important for the MFI to recruit a leadership team that understands its chosen market. But given that women are often at the lowest income level in developing countries, the advantage of having women in leadership positions should also carry over to the rural/urban measure and average loan.

Institutions. The institutional variables are the MFI's regulatory status, its founding status (internationally initiated or not), the competition in its product market, and its ownership type. MFIs are diversely incorporated, covering ordinary shareholder-owned firms, mutually held institutions (COOP), non-governmental organizations⁵ (NGOs), and state banks. We use two indicator variables, one indicating the MFI is an NGO, the other indicating it is a COOP. The ownership variable is potentially important, since women may more easily enter leadership positions in the often more mission-driven NGOs and COOPs. The competition variable is the rater's assessment of the MFIs' competitive challenge in its area, and converted to a common scale of 1 to 7. Finally, 36% of the MFIs in our sample are internationally initiated (prodded to start by a Western organization). This rich institutional background provides an opportunity for studying female leadership under a diversity of external conditions. Mersland and Strøm (2009) find that these institutional variables are not related to the MFI's financial performance, but did not investigate governance issues.

MFI and country controls. Aguilera and Jackson (2010) point out that country specific traditions and institutions can be important in corporate governance studies. We include a number of MFI level and country level variables for the governance and performance regressions in order to account for MFI heterogeneity. The firm level controls are the MFI's

⁵ MFIs incorporated as Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) are not-for-profit firms where no particular group or person can legally claim ownership of it or receive residual earnings from it (Mersland, 2009).

age, the portfolio at risk (more than 30 days outstanding), and the MFI's size. The specification of size is the natural logarithm of total assets, which reduces outlier bias. We expect that the larger the MFI is, the more complex it becomes, and the more it will adopt formal governance mechanisms, that is, monitoring becomes more important and advising less. The MFI's age is an important control variable, since an MFI is likely to learn what governance mechanisms work and how to achieve profitability⁶. Last, the risk is specified as the default rate, that is, the fraction of the portfolio 30 days overdue. Cultural predispositions are likely to be found between countries. The country control variable includes the Human Development Index (HDI) from UN's Development Programme. Furthermore, GDP per capita (adjusted for purchasing power parity), GDP growth, and the Heritage Foundation's index of economic freedom enter regressions as controls along with the HDI index. Finally, we check for country differences in gender inequalities by including the UN index GII (gender inequality index).

The 73 countries rank low on development indices, and are highly dispersed. Appendix A shows the countries in our sample, the frequency of MFIs in each country and also in main world regions. The MFIs in our sample range from countries ranked 35 (Argentina) to 135 (Niger) in 1998 and from 39 (Chile) to 134 (Democratic Republic of Congo) in 2008 out of 135 countries in the HDI. Thus, the MFIs in our sample are situated in developing countries. At the same time, the heterogeneity within the sample with respect to the home country's development level underlines the need for country controls.

The emphasis on choosing a female leadership is not limited to particular segments of countries in our sample. This is evident from the scores on HDI and the gender inequality

⁶ The oldest MFI in our sample is DCC bank in India which started to offer microfinance services in the early 1920s.

index (GII), see table 2. The percentage of female leadership categories in different world regions is set out in the lower part of the table.

Table 2

The table shows that only for the female CEO the score difference is significant in panel A, and even this at the rather low 10% significance level. Thus, we cannot find clear country differences with respect to female leadership. Likewise, the female CEO differences across world regions are significant, but not the female chair and the female director. The lowest incidence of female leadership in any category is in the Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA) region. Appendix A shows that the EECA countries constitute 19.5% of the sample. Evidently, table 2 shows that controlling for country or regional differences is important. But the table also shows that female leadership is not confined to a particular region, but shows a fairly similar pattern in all regions. The female leadership similarity and country controls should ensure that our results are not driven by specific conditions in a few countries.

We run multivariate regressions to analyze relationships. There is always a danger that multicollinearity occurs in such a setting. Furthermore, we run corporate governance mechanisms and financial performance analyses separately. A first way to check for multicollinearity and independence is to run a correlation analysis for the main explanatory variables.

Table 3

Kennedy (2008) puts the danger level for multicollinearity to a correlation between two variables at about 0.80. Only the correlation between the MFI's assets and its loan portfolio reported in table 3 reaches this level. This simply means that these variables are substitute definitions of the MFI's size. The next highest levels are found between the financial performance variables, the highest being 0.75 between ROA and ROE. This is as expected.

Since the remaining correlations are low, the explanatory variables used in regressions are independent on a satisfactory level, that is, they may be used independently of each other. The table also shows that the correlations between corporate governance mechanisms and financial performance variables are weak, the highest being 0.22 between OSS and the number of board meetings. This result is in fact in line with Mersland and Strøm (2009) who find hardly any significant relationships between governance variables and the MFI's financial performance. This indicates that governance and financial performance variables may be run independently, which is the procedure we follow here. Nevertheless, we run robustness checks on the potential relationships between governance and financial performance. These robustness checks parallel the testing procedure in Adams and Ferreira (2009).

4. METHODOLOGY

We use a straightforward probit method to predict the female leadership variables. Thus, in the case of the female CEO we run the probit regression:

$$Pr(\text{Female CEO}) = f(\text{Social mission, Institutions, Controls, Errors}) \quad (1)$$

and then similar regressions for the chair and female directors. This relation has an interest in itself, but is also fundamental in financial performance regressions where female leadership may be endogenously determined.

When either a corporate governance (CG) variable or a financial performance (FP) variable is the dependent, the basic estimating relation is as follows for the case of return on assets (ROA):

$$ROA = f(\text{Female leadership, MFI controls, Country controls, Errors}) \quad (2)$$

The corporate governance variables are meetings, internal auditor, CEO duality, and board size. Financial performance is one of the financial performance measures (ROA, ROE, OSS or FSS). The CEO and the chair variables are both dichotomous. We also turn the female director variable into an indicator variable in the main regressions. For the governance regressions we use the probit method when the governance mechanism is dichotomous (internal auditor, CEO duality), and tobit-censored regressions for the discrete governance variables (board meeting and board size). For instance, the board size has a truncated distribution, since it cannot be smaller than 1. The financial performance regressions are performed with instruments in two different setups that we explain below. All regressions are performed with a constant, but this constant is not reported.

In the financial performance estimations we build upon the Heckman (1979) endogenous dummy variable model and follow the two-step procedure laid out by Wooldridge (2010, p. 937-945). In the first step, an instrument for each female leadership indicator variable is generated from (1). This is the probability that a given MFI has a female CEO, say. The extracted probability is then used in the second step random effects model as an instrument for female leadership, say the female CEO.

The two-step method yields the added advantage that female leadership is regressed on variables that are likely to proxy for the match with female leadership. This concerns social mission variables, such as the MFI's gender bias, but also institutional variables, such as the MFI's ownership type. The generated instrument, that is, the likelihood that the CEO is female, is likely to be highly correlated with the female CEO, but not with any measure of financial performance. Wooldridge (2010) furthermore shows that the generating regression (1) does not need to be correctly specified in order to generate a useful instrument.

The two-step method has the further advantage that an inverse Mill's ratio test for endogeneity due to sample selection is easily devised. Sample selection may arise in our context if it is the case that some able women do not seek leadership positions in the MFIs, despite being as qualified as the observed female CEO and directors.

Wooldridge (2010, p. 809-813) shows how a general test for sample selection can be performed. In our case, when the female leadership category under consideration is endogenous, the first step is to estimate (1) as before. From this estimation one saves the predicted values for the likelihood that the CEO is female. This is the inverse Mill's ratio. The second step is to insert this predicted variable into the financial performance regressions (2). If the predicted variable is significant, measured by an ordinary t-test, there is a case for sample selection.

In both the governance and financial performance regressions a number of control variables are included so as to remove MFI specific heterogeneity as much as possible. First of all, we estimate with MFI clustered standard errors to correct for heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation. This alone in fact takes away most of the MFI level heterogeneity (Petersen, 2009). Furthermore, the MFI level and country level variables control for country heterogeneity among MFIs. Last, we include indicator variables for the main world regions, defined in table 2, and for time. Time indicator variables control for market-wide impacts in financial performance regressions. With panel data, instruments, and a wide set of control variables the estimations should at least vouch for reliable correlations, but perhaps causality only in the financial performance regressions, where we have taken account of the endogeneity of female leadership.

We report on robustness checks in section 8 varying estimation method, variable specification, especially the female director, and the use of lagged variables. Estimations in

Adams and Ferreira (2009) and in Carter et al. (2010) show that results are not robust to estimation method. For instance, the Adams and Ferreira results vary with OLS, fixed effects at industry and firm level methods, and finally, with a two-stage least squares IV method. We specify a different IV model for the financial performance estimations, where instruments are the significant variables in the regressions of female leadership on background variables in relationship (1). We check for the validity of the instruments with the Sargan test of overidentifying restrictions.

Adams and Ferreira (2009) and Carter et al. (2010) also show that the financial performance results may be sensitive to the definition of female director. We perform regressions with different definitions. In particular, we examine the Konrad et al. (2008) critical mass theory with an indicator variable being one if the number of female directors is equal to or larger than three. Other female director measures put to the test are the percentage of female directors and the absolute number of female directors.

Governance and financial performance may be closely related, although the correlation matrix in table 3 and evidence in Mersland and Strøm (2009) cast doubt if this is the case in microfinance. In the Hermalin and Weisbach (1998) model board independence is endogenously determined by past performance. Accordingly, Adams and Ferreira (2009) always use governance and financial performance variables together in regressions. We run two robustness checks for governance importance. The first is for governance variables where former financial performance is an explanatory variable. In the second robustness check we include governance mechanisms among the explanatory variables in financial performance regressions.

Adams et al. (2010) recommend the fixed effects method for panel data, which will remove time-invariant heterogeneity in the data completely, but then recommend the random effects

model if the board attribute enters nonlinearly, and if different firms face differently shaped tradeoffs between governance mechanisms. Our random effects methodology with MFI level standard errors specifications are linear, but also MFI specific. Furthermore, a number of our explanatory variables are themselves time-invariant, and would be wiped out with fixed effects. This concerns the female leadership variables. Accordingly, the random effects method is our preferred method.

The microfinance promise (Morduch, 1999) says that the MFI follows its social mission to offer financial services to the poor while being financially sustainable. This could pose a problem for estimations, if there is a large, negative correlation between financial performance and outreach to poor customers. In our sample, the correlation between ROA and average loan is only 0.111, indicating goal independence. This lack of correlation allows separate regressions for governance mechanisms and financial performance. Nevertheless, we include social mission variables to control for any influence.

5. THE MATCH OF FEMALE LEADERSHIP AND THE MFI

The first step in the IV procedure outlined above is to generate the probability that the leader in the MFI is female. We test the hypothesis that female leadership is more likely the greater weight the MFI places on its social mission. This concerns first and foremost the MFI's gender bias, but also the MFI's choice of urban and rural market and its average loan size.

We use straightforward probit regressions for the CEO and chair regressions and OLS regression for the female director fraction using data from the rating year. We have related the three female leadership roles of CEO, chair, and director to the background characteristics of

MFIs and a country control⁷, first by using the whole sample, and then using the sample for the rating year only. The results appear in Table 4.

Table 4

Table 4 shows that female leadership is more likely in MFIs that have a gender bias toward female clients, in MFIs concentrating on the urban market, in NGOs and cooperatives more than in shareholder-owned MFIs (the omitted category), and in younger MFIs. However, a female CEO is less likely when the MFI has an international founder, while a female chair is less likely when competition is high.

It is remarkable that gender bias and ownership type are significant for all three categories of female leadership for the full sample, and that the signs are the same. Gender bias is significant in all leadership categories in the rating year regressions as well. Ownership type is significant as well in the rating year regressions, except for NGOs. Thus, the MFI's choices of social mission and its ownership structure are important for understanding the extent of female leadership. The instrument we generate can therefore be used in governance and performance regressions.

The matching regressions from the relationship (1) have parallels to the papers on the endogeneity of boards, e.g. Boone et al. (2007), and may contribute to the understanding of the emergence of female leadership in MFIs. Some of the variables are truly exogenous, this concerns first and foremost the internationally initiated and the firm age variables, but also ownership type, regulation and the social mission orientation are variables that hardly change.

⁷ The results are unaffected when the HDI control is replaced by the Heritage index or by a more elaborate set of country controls including per capita GDP and GDP growth.

6. FEMALE LEADERSHIP AND CORPORATE GOVERNANCE

Is internal governance better in MFIs with women as the CEO, chair, or director? We perform regressions with the governance variables as dependent and the female leadership variables as independent and also include control variables and regional dummies⁸. Each female leadership variable is introduced into the regression, one at the time. Table 5 gives an overview.

Table 5

The overall statistics are satisfactory, with high F and Wald chi-square statistics throughout. Thus, we cannot uphold the hypothesis that all explanatory variables are insignificant in the regressions.

Contrary to our expectations concerning the advantageous match between female leadership and MFI governance, Table 5 suggests that female leadership is generally associated with *weaker* corporate governance. A female CEO is negatively related to board meetings but positively to the board size, the female chair and director are negatively related to internal audits, but positively to CEO duality. The female director is positively related to board size. The findings are at odds with those of Adams and Ferreira (2009), who find that female directors bring about better governance practices, although they use different measures, in particular board attendance. We cannot confirm the evidence from a review of Canadian governance (Brown et al., 2002) that “boards with more women surpass all-male boards in their attention to audit and risk oversight and control”. Rather, the negative association with better governance by all female leadership categories, not only the CEO, suggests that mechanisms for CEO monitoring have low value in female-led MFIs.

⁸ In this regression no time-dummies are taken up since the governance variables in our dataset do generally not vary over time.

A number of the control variables have interesting implications, and are generally in line with former research linking governance variables to firms' market conditions (Baker and Gompers, 2003; Boone et al., 2007; Linck et al., 2008). MFI size in terms of lnTA is highly significant in all regressions, inducing more meetings, more often an internal auditor and CEO duality, and a larger board. The MFI's age is likewise highly significant, but the MFI is likely to split the CEO and chair role as the MFI gets older. Thus, corporate governance becomes more important as the MFI is larger and older. This seems reasonable, since formalization often tends to overtake the entrepreneurial spirit as the firm matures. The internal auditor results confirm Hay et al. (2006), that is, the same variables are important for *internal* audits. We also find that the COOP ownership type comes in combination with more board meetings, less often internal auditor, more often CEO duality, and a larger board. The same is true for the NGO ownership form, except for the number of meetings. Thus, in more complex ownership structures such as the COOP, governance is discharged by a large board meeting frequently, and not to supporting mechanisms such as the internal auditor. It appears that in member owned firms the members control the firm by sitting on the boards in frequent meetings. Thus, the CEO's power position is strengthened by the lack of internal auditor and the CEO's presence at the board, but curtailed by a large board in frequent meetings. Our ownership type variables confirm the main result in Desender et al. (2009), who compare widely and closely held firms. These findings indicate that our control variables are highly relevant in this study.

Table 5 shows that the country variable GDP growth is significant and positive in the regressions for board meetings and internal auditor, and that the Heritage Foundation Index is positively related to CEO duality and board size. More meetings and better internal auditing are plausible in a high-growth environment. Thus, country differences are evident for

corporate governance, supporting Terjesen and Singh (2008), and complement the female leadership findings.

7. FEMALE LEADERSHIP AND PERFORMANCE

How is female leadership linked to MFI performance? Is the match of the female leadership with social mission oriented MFIs advantageous for financial performance? Table 6 shows the results when we use the Heckman (1979) model for an endogenous indicator variable, the female leadership categories being the indicator variable, and the probabilities of being for instance a female CEO derived from regressions in table 4.

Table 6

The Wald chi-squared test shows that we cannot leave all explanatory variables out of the specification. The inverse Mill's ratio is not significant in any of the regressions, thus, our estimations do not suffer from sample selection bias⁹.

The female CEO is positively and significantly related to financial performance for three out of four measures, confirming our expectations and Mersland and Strøm (2009). The female chair and female director are also significant with a positive sign in three out of four regressions. Thus, results are remarkably similar across manager and director roles. Shrader et al. (1997), Smith et al. (2006), and Francoeur et al. (2008) find that performance is enhanced with a female CEO, but reduced with female directors. Adams and Ferreira (2009) also find that female directors overall have a negative impact upon performance. However, our findings for female leadership in general support arguments for high ability among female MFI leaders due to a superior match of leadership and tasks.

⁹ The IMR-test was performed for all IV-regressions, we did not find any evidence of sample selection bias.

The firm controls show that the firm effects are reasonable, being positive for MFI size, negative for age, and negative for default risk. The only occasionally significant country effects are neither surprising in view of Allen and Gale (2000) finding that firm performance is quite similar across financial systems of the world. Thus, from table 5 and 6 we find that country idiosyncracies partly associate with governing mechanisms, but few such associations are detectable for financial performance.

8. ROBUSTNESS

How reliable are the above results? In this section, we report various robustness checks for the estimation method and variable specification. This is motivated by the diversity of results in the literature depending on the method used or the variable specification.

In the first robustness test we use a different instrumental variables method for financial performance, where instruments are taken from the significant variables in the matching regressions in table 4. At the same time, we use the fraction of female directors as our definition. Table 7 reports the results.

Table 7

The signs are everywhere the same as in table 6, but the significant results are fewer in this case. The MFI control variables behave much as in table 6 as well. The Sargan test tells us that instruments are relevant for these estimations¹⁰. Thus, overall, the results in table 6 are robust to the estimation method used.

¹⁰ In Table 7, we have 2 out of 12 regressions were at the 10% significance level in the ROA regressions. Table 8 shows significance levels at 1% and 2% in two OSS regressions. Thus, the null hypothesis of no overidentifying restrictions cannot be upheld in these cases.

Ambivalent results for the female director in former research motivate alternative tests employing different specifications of the female director. In particular, we examine the Konrad et al. (2008) critical mass hypothesis that there needs to be at least three female directors to realize their positive impact in full. We implement this with an indicator variable being one if the number of female directors is equal to or larger than three. Other female director measures put to the test are a binary variable for a gender mixed board and the absolute number of female directors. Table 8 reports the results.

Table 8

It turns out that the new specifications of the female director give significant results only for the FSS measure. Thus, we cannot confirm the critical mass theory or other specifications of the female director. The overall findings on the female director variable are inconsistent, partly driven by different specifications of the variable. Thus, we confirm findings in Carter et al. (2010) that the definition of female director matters. This implies that different definitions of female director may cause the different result we find in the literature.

Next, we turn to the possible link between governance and financial performance, as the Hermalin and Weisbach (1998) model suggests. We add the lagged ROA to the set of right hand side variables and rerun table 5 in the female CEO and chair regressions. Results are set out in table 9.

Table 9

We find no significant relationships between the lagged ROA and governance. Given the very low correlations in table 3 between governance and financial performance variables this comes as no surprise. Also, the results in table 9 confirm findings in Mersland and Strøm (2009), where internal governance mechanisms are not associated with financial performance.

These findings support the regression specifications we have used here, treating governance and financial performance in separate estimations.

Finally, we turn the question around following Adams and Ferreira (2009) in including corporate governance variables into the financial performance regressions. We include board meetings and board size among the explanatory variables in the financial performance regressions, using the Heckman (1979) dummy endogenous variable method from table 6. The regressions are set out in table 10.

Table 10

We find only a weak relationship in the OSS regressions when the female director is taken to be the female leadership variable. This means that our results from table 9 are upheld, and that we do not risk much in not including governance mechanisms in our main financial performance regressions in table 6. An interesting result in table 10 is that the female CEO relates significantly to ROA when the board size is in the regression. This is in fact the same result that Mersland and Strøm (2009) obtain, supporting again the enhanced financial performance in female-led MFIs.

In unreported regressions we use winsorized data, but find no material difference in results from those presented here. Furthermore, we also tried regressions without the GDP Growth and regressions with interactions between governance variables and ownership type. None of these robustness regressions gave results that differ from those reported.

The overall conclusion of the robustness checks is that our results are confirmed when we vary estimation method, variable definition for female director, and regression specifications. Thus, our conclusions from the governance and financial performance sections are upheld.

9. CONCLUSIONS

Microfinance institutions (MFI) are remarkable in that they hire more female CEOs and elect more female chairs and female directors than firms in advanced countries. An MFI's mission is to supply loans to low-income families and small businesses, especially women, in the developing world, and it aims to do so in a financially sustainable manner (Morduch, 1999). This paper investigates the conditions under which female leadership tends to emerge, and the relationships between female leadership and corporate governance, as found in Adams and Ferreira (2009), and its association with the MFIs' financial performance. Unlike other studies, that often include only directors, ours specify female leadership as a female CEO, chair, or director. The data are hand-collected from third-party raters' reports on 329 MFIs in 73 countries, and each MFI rating report provides information for up to six years.

Three main conclusions emerge from the investigation. The first concerns the conditions under which female leadership is generally found. Female leadership increases with the MFI's mission to supply credit particularly to women, with being a cooperative or a NGO. However, having an international founder tends to reduce female leadership. This supports the matching argument from the Becker (1973) model in the sense that female CEOs are indeed matched with gender biased MFIs.

The second main conclusion deals with the relationships between female leadership and corporate governance. Unlike Adams and Ferreira (2009), we find female leadership to be associated with weaker corporate governance, since board meetings are fewer, internal audits less common, and CEO duality more common when women hold leadership positions.

Finally, the third main conclusion confirms the findings of Shrader et al. (1997), Smith et al. (2006), and Francoeur et al. (2008) that female CEOs are positively related to firms' financial performance. This also applies to female directors, adding evidence to the just mentioned

studies and also to Adams and Ferreira (2009). We also find that the female chair performance effect is similar to that of the female CEO; financial performance is better in MFIs with a female chair. The conclusion is that in an industry largely catering for female customers, having female leadership is likely to improve the MFI's financial performance. Taken together with the negative relationship between female leadership and governance mechanisms, this means that female-led MFIs perform better with less oversight, less monitoring. The upshot is that the quality of leadership is decisive in microfinance institutions.

We believe the contrasting governance and financial performance results are due to the fact that MFIs are young, entrepreneurial firms. The optimal governance form has perhaps not been settled. Furthermore, the abilities of the individual CEO are pivotal in this rapidly expanding segment. Future research would benefit from exploring the extent and the implications of the female leadership attribute, like education and experience, in more detail. Future research could also fruitfully explore whether female leadership is better at meeting the MFI's outreach goals than male.

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Table 1. Summary statistics for the variables used in this study. The number of observations (N) is stated in terms of firms for categorical variables and firm-years for continuous variables.

		N	Mean	Median	St. Dev.	Min.	Max.
Female leadership							
Female CEO	Binary: 1 if female CEO	329	0.27	0.00	0.44	0.00	1.00
Female chair	Binary: 1 if female chair	238	0.23	0.00	0.42	0.00	1.00
Female director	Binary: 1 if one or more female directors	167	0.75	1.00	0.44	0.00	1.00
# female directors	Number of female directors	148	1.69	1.00	1.76	0.00	9.00
Female dir. fraction	Female directors as fraction of all directors	148	0.29	0.20	0.28	0.00	1.00
Dumfemdir≥3	Binary: 1 if # female directors is 3 or more	148	0.23	0.00	0.42	0.00	1.00
Corporate governance							
Meetings	Number of annual board meetings	197	7.64	4.00	7.51	1.00	52.00
CEO duality	Binary: 1 if CEO and chair are same person	304	0.15	0.00	0.36	0.00	1.00
Internal audit	Binary: 1 if MFI has an internal auditor	280	0.39	0.00	0.49	0.00	1.00
Board size	Number of directors	303	7.04	6.00	3.48	1.00	23.00
Financial performance							
ROA	Return on assets	1,075	0.010	0.022	0.11	-0.89	0.34
ROE	Return on equity	987	0.053	0.070	0.27	-0.91	0.56
OSS	Operational self-sufficiency	1,061	1.56	1.49	0.68	0.004	3.00
FSS	Financial self-sufficiency	667	0.96	0.96	0.37	0.06	3.00
General characteristics							
TA	Total assets (USD 1,000)	1,125	5,365	2,227	9,856	19.288	144,000
TLP	Total loan portfolio (USD 1,000)	1,140	3,786	1,665	5,801	3.425	59,700
PaR30	Fraction of loan portfolio 30 days overdue	1,043	0.066	0.034	0.094	0.000	0.973
Average loan	TLP divided by credit clients	1,037	734	351	1,330	1.00	24.589
Age	Number of years in operation	1,081	9.36	8.00	7.23	0.00	79.00
Rural	Binary: 1 if emphasized area is rural	319	0.26	0.00	0.43	0.00	1.00
Urban	Binary: 1 if emphasized area is urban	319	0.30	0.00	0.46	0.00	1.00
Gender bias	Binary: 1 if priority is on female clients	324	0.44	0.00	0.49	0.00	1.00
Regulated	Binary: 1 if regulated by banking authority	322	0.25	0.00	0.43	0.00	1.00
Internationally initiated	Binary: 1 if internationally initiated	327	0.36	0.00	0.48	0.00	1.00
NGO	Binary: 1 if type is NGO	329	0.52	1.00	0.50	0.00	1.00
COOP	Binary: 1 if type is cooperative	329	0.16	0.00	0.36	0.00	1.00
Competition index	Index from no comp. (1) to high comp. (7)	303	4.26	4.00	1.54	1.00	7.00

Table 2: Female leadership and mean scores on the human development index (HDI) and the gender inequality index (GII) in Panel A and the percentage of female leadership categories in world regions in Panel B. Higher HDI value means higher development, a higher GII value means more inequality. HDI is an average over relevant years for the MFI, the GII is indexed in 2008. Source: UN Development Programme and own data.

<i>Table A</i>	Female		
	CEO	Chair	director
GII:			
No	0.653	0.639	0.602
Yes	0.639	0.642	0.629
t-test mean difference	1.276	-0.147	-1.352
MFI	295	214	133
HDI:			
No	0.604	0.626	0.660
Yes	0.633	0.625	0.651
t-test mean difference	-1.820*	0.048	0.423
MFI	325	235	147
<i>Table B</i>			
Region:			
Latin America	31.3	26.7	73.5
Africa	24.1	19.7	76.5
MENA	36.4	29.6	75.0
EECA	14.1	11.6	60.7
Asia	34.8	28.1	82.4
Total	27.1	22.7	73.0
MFI	329	238	148
Chisqrd(4)	9.60**	5.27	3.15

The HDI combines indicators of life expectancy, educational attainment (mean of years of schooling for adults aged 25 years and expected years of schooling for children of school going age) and income (the logarithm of GNI per capita (PPP USD)) into a composite human development index. The GII includes three main components, reproductive health (maternal mortality and adolescent fertility), empowerment (parliamentary attainment and educational attainment) and labour market (labour force participation rate). EECA is Eastern Europe and Central Asia; MENA is Middle East and North Africa. One star signifies significance at 10% level, two stars at 5%.

Table 3. Correlation matrix. Pairwise correlations between all continuous variables

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
1 # fem. dir.													
2 meetings	-0.06												
3 board size	0.33	-0.11											
4 Roa	-0.11	-0.06	0.02										
5 Roe	-0.03	-0.06	0.08	0.75									
6 Oss	-0.08	0.22	0.01	0.51	0.51								
7 Fss	-0.13	0.02	0.07	0.65	0.50	0.43							
8 TA	-0.01	-0.01	0.04	0.07	0.13	0.18	0.17						
9 TLP	-0.01	-0.01	0.01	0.08	0.14	0.20	0.18	0.98					
10 par30	-0.04	0.18	-0.17	-0.09	-0.08	-0.01	-0.22	-0.10	-0.12				
11 average loan	-0.12	0.19	-0.09	-0.01	0.10	0.38	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.01			
12 Age	0.01	0.30	-0.05	-0.11	-0.19	-0.04	-0.01	0.23	0.19	0.26	-0.08		

Variables are defined in table 1.

Table 4. Female leadership and MFI characteristics. We analyze the characteristics that are associated with female leadership in terms of a female CEO, a female chair, a female director, and the fraction of female directors (continuous) by means of pooled probit regressions and pooled OLS. Significance levels are based upon standard errors corrected for autocorrelation and heteroskedasticity. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

Dep. Var	All observations			Rating year only		
	Fem. CEO	Fem. Chair	Fem. dir. fraction	Fem. CEO	Fem. Chair	Fem. dir. fraction
<i>Social mission</i>						
Gender bias	0.445***	0.912***	0.122***	0.389**	0.901***	0.118*
Urban	0.137*	0.202*	0.002	0.059	0.292*	0.017
ln(Average loan)	-0.072	0.083	-0.010	-0.095	0.061	0.002
<i>Institutional variables</i>						
Regulated	0.125	0.281	-0.103***	0.095	0.371	-0.074
Competition	-0.056	-0.065*	-0.008	-0.067	-0.092	-0.021
Int. initiated	-0.395***	-0.127	0.022	-0.358**	-0.064	0.021
NGO	0.378**	0.320*	0.081**	0.128*	0.566*	0.051
COOP	0.494***	0.235**	0.325***	0.436**	0.492*	0.232**
<i>Firm / country controls</i>						
Age	-0.009*	-0.027***	-0.001	-0.004	-0.041**	0.001
PaR30	-0.869	0.229	-0.006	-0.190	0.331	0.015
LnTA	-0.011	-0.118**	-0.032**	-0.049	-0.011	-0.039
HDI	0.734*	-0.964	-0.223*	1.113*	-0.562	-0.427
N	731	536	332	254	178	106
Wald χ^2 / F-stat	57.30***	87.83***	9.78***	18.86*	32.20***	2.42***
Pseudo-R ²	0.07	0.12	0.25	0.07	0.14	0.17
Method	Probit	Probit	OLS	Probit	Probit	OLS

Table 5. Female leadership and corporate governance. We regress corporate governance on female leadership and controls. Governance is measured through the number of board meetings, a binary for internal audits, and a binary for CEO duality and the number of board members. For the binary governance variables probit regressions are estimated, for the discrete governance variables, tobit-censored regressions are estimated. Significance levels are based on heteroskedastic and autocorrelation-corrected standard errors. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

	<i>Meetings</i>				<i>Internal Audit</i>			
female leadership								
Female CEO	-1.401***				0.058			
Female chair		-0.760				-0.282**		
Fraction fem. dir.			-3.034				-1.336***	
Female director				-1.016				-0.429***
MFI controls								
lnTA	0.858***	0.764**	0.976**	1.017***	0.328***	0.265***	0.408***	0.381***
Age	0.191***	0.221***	0.167**	0.158**	0.013**	0.023***	0.019**	0.022**
PaR30	0.900	0.370	0.032	0.063	-0.335	-0.773	-0.115	-0.068
Competition	-0.024	-0.297	-0.383	-0.326	0.056*	0.002	-0.049	0.023
NGO	-0.371	-0.686	-0.558	-0.341	-0.649***	-0.768***	-0.515**	-0.658***
COOP	5.827***	5.121***	5.997***	6.086***	-0.596***	-0.621***	-0.124*	-0.702***
country controls								
GDPpercapita	0.002	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001
Heritage	-0.079*	-0.056	-0.056	-0.041	-0.001	0.001	-0.021	-0.009
GDPgrowth	24.166***	20.009***	19.841**	19.086***	1.421	3.470**	1.823	1.408
regional dummies								
	<i>incl.</i>	<i>incl.</i>	<i>incl.</i>	<i>incl.</i>	<i>incl.</i>	<i>incl.</i>	<i>incl.</i>	<i>incl.</i>
N	591	458	336	370	863	623	405	467
F stat. / Wald χ^2	12.27***	12.40***	11.96***	10.03***	181.28***	131.79***	129.40***	150.62***
R ²	0.06	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.19	0.17	0.29	0.24
Method	Tobit	Tobit	Tobit	Tobit	Probit	Probit	Probit	Probit

Table 5 continued

	<i>CEO Duality</i>				<i>Board size</i>			
<i>female leadership</i>								
Female CEO	0.082				0.761**			
Female chair		0.208				-0.309		
Fraction fem. dir.			0.746**				-0.293	
Female director				0.275*				1.052***
<i>MFI controls</i>								
lnTA	0.209***	0.253***	0.263***	0.216***	0.484***	0.524***	0.423***	0.328***
Age	-0.026***	-0.034***	-0.074***	-0.039***	-0.009	0.001	-0.042***	-0.051***
PaR30	-0.131	0.100	0.988	0.359	-0.721	0.406	-0.343	-0.552
Competition	-0.043	-0.031	0.162	0.035	-0.571***	-0.601***	-0.239***	-0.273***
NGO	0.261**	0.208*	0.029	0.131	1.941***	2.221***	1.132***	1.095***
COOP	0.523***	0.554***	0.946***	0.654***	2.157***	1.772***	1.552***	1.426***
<i>country controls</i>								
GDPpercapita	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001
Heritage	0.037***	0.041***	0.026**	0.034***	0.042***	0.043**	0.019	0.041**
GDPgrowth	-2.079	-2.901	-0.453	-2.062	-2.398	0.598	-1.745	-1.985
<i>regional dummies</i>								
	<i>incl.</i>	<i>incl.</i>	<i>incl.</i>	<i>incl.</i>	<i>incl.</i>	<i>incl.</i>	<i>incl.</i>	<i>incl.</i>
N	910	685	392	453	883	646	447	500
F stat. / Wald χ^2	71.06***	71.77***	58.29***	46.66***	16.24***	12.48***	6.47***	10.16***
R ²	0.10	0.11	0.14	0.09	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Method	Probit	Probit	Probit	Probit	Tobit	Tobit	Tobit	Tobit

Table 6. Female leadership and performance: a two-step experiment setting.

Financial performance in terms of ROE, ROA (panel A), OSS and FSS (panel B) regressed on female leadership, MFI and country controls using IV. As instruments, fitted probabilities from a probit analysis explaining the dummy female CEO, dummy female CHAIR and dummy female DIRECTOR have been used, in the dummy endogenous variable model of Heckman (1979). Significance levels based on heteroskedastic and autocorrelation-corrected standard errors clustered at the MFI level. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

panel A	ROE			ROA		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
female leadership						
Female CEO	0.189**			0.035		
Female CHAIR		0.178*			0.104***	
Female DIRECTOR			0.152			0.092*
MFI controls						
lnTA	0.070***	0.072***	0.059***	0.027***	0.024***	0.019**
Age	-0.005**	-0.002	-0.007*	-0.001*	0.004	-0.001
par30	-0.218**	-0.026	-0.062	-0.216***	-0.043	-0.004
country controls						
GDP per capita	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Heritage	-0.002	-0.002	-0.003	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001
GDP growth	0.226	0.082	0.237	0.298**	0.298*	0.402*
regional dummies	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
time dummies	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
model statistics						
N	608	456	348	649	485	366
R ²	0.13	0.12	0.09	0.17	0.14	0.13
Wald χ^2	920.72***	27.77***	21.59***	121.87***	32.10***	24.07***
IMR-test	0.137	-0.247	-0.133	0.082	-0.168	-0.137
<i>Instruments: fitted probabilities from a probit explaining binary variables for female CEO, female chair, and female director</i>						

Table 6 continued

panel B	OSS			FSS		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
female leadership						
Female CEO	0.196*			0.302**		
Female CHAIR		0.013			0.396**	
Female DIRECTOR			0.428*			0.549*
MFI controls						
lnTA	0.216***	0.213***	0.212***	0.101***	0.112***	0.121***
Age	-0.004	0.003	0.003	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001
par30	-0.384	-0.501	-0.351	-0.648***	-0.741***	-0.729***
country controls						
GDP per capita	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Heritage	-0.017	-0.023	-0.018*	-0.005	-0.007	-0.006
GDP growth	0.35	0.045	0.154	0.088	-0.13	-0.042
regional dummies	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
time dummies	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
model statistics						
N	647	489	371	455	388	388
R ²	0.23	0.21	0.21	0.17	0.17	0.17
Wald χ^2	239.11***	79.86***	456.19***	72.18***	352.66***	116.97***
IMR-test	0.101	-0.479	-0.169	0.213	-0.201	-0.249
<i>Instruments: fitted probabilities from a probit explaining binary variables for female CEO, female chair, and female director</i>						

Table 7. Female leadership and performance. An instrumental variables approach to determine whether female leadership stimulates financial performance. We regress financial performance on female leadership using 2SLS. For instruments, the variables that have a clear relation with female leadership according to Table 4 have been used. The validity of the instruments is tested using the Sargan test of overidentifying restrictions. Significance levels are based on heteroskedastic and autocorrelation-corrected standard errors clustered at the MFI level. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

Panel A	ROE			ROA		
female leadership						
Female CEO	0.202**			0.136		
Female chair		0.167*			0.024	
Fraction fem. dir.			0.245			0.016
MFI controls						
lnTA	0.067***	0.067***	0.063***	0.029***	0.025***	0.021**
Age	-0.005**	-0.002	-0.006**	-0.001	-0.001	-0.002
PaR30	-0.266	-0.024	0.036	-0.243**	-0.076*	-0.095
country controls						
GDPpercapita	-0.001	0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001
Heritage	-0.002	-0.001	-0.002	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001
GDPgrowth	0.254	0.027	0.189	0.381*	0.254*	0.396**
regional dummies	included	included	included	included	included	included
time dummies	included	included	included	included	included	included
model statistics						
N	775	577	377	839	629	406
R ²	0.12	0.12	0.10	0.20	0.16	0.17
Wald χ^2	98.57***	27.40***	116.79***	61.71***	92.74***	270.10***
Sargan stat.	1.670	4.195	2.920	6.884	6.786	3.076
Sargan p-value	0.64	0.24	0.40	0.07	0.08	0.38
Instruments used						
<i>ownership type, internationally initiated, dumrural, gender bias</i>						

Table 7 continued

Panel B	OSS			FSS		
female leadership						
Female CEO	0.175*			0.423**		
Female chair		0.034			0.487**	
Fraction fem. dir.			0.116			0.694**
MFI controls						
lnTA	0.212***	0.204***	0.191***	0.117***	0.131***	0.121***
Age	-0.005	-0.004	-0.002	-0.003	-0.003	-0.004
PaR30	0.191	0.345	0.341	-0.662**	-0.724***	-0.549*
country controls						
GDPpercapita	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
Heritage	-0.014***	-0.018**	-0.011	-0.001	-0.001	-0.005
GDPgrowth	0.965	0.502	0.150	0.048	0.016	0.478
regional dummies	included	included	included	included	included	included
time dummies	included	included	included	included	included	included
model statistics						
N	842	638	408	553	471	360
R ²	0.25	0.19	0.22	0.15	0.14	0.18
Wald χ^2	420.30***	116.74***	122.12***	64.25***	82.24***	727.11***
Sargan stat.	1.979	6.684	5.126	4.659	2.083	1.878
Sargan p-value	0.19	0.15	0.16	0.20	0.56	0.60
Instruments used						
<i>ownership type, internationally initiated, dumrural, gender bias</i>						

Table 8. Instrumental variables performance regressions with different definitions for female director.

Fraction fem.dir. is the percentage female directors. # female directors is a continuous variable denoting the number of female directors. Dumfemdir ≥ 3 is a dummy that is 1 if the MFI has three or more female directors. For instruments, the variables that have a clear relation with female leadership according to Table 4 have been used. The validity of the instruments is tested using the Sargan test of overidentifying restrictions. Significance levels are based on heteroskedastic and autocorrelation-corrected standard errors clustered at the MFI level. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively. Year dummies and country controls are included.

Panel A	ROE			ROA		
fraction fem. dir.	0.245			0.016		
# female directors		0.025			0.008	
dumfemdir ≥ 3			0.071			0.013
lnTA	0.063***	0.058***	0.056***	0.021**	0.021***	0.021***
Age	-0.006**	-0.006*	-0.007**	-0.002	-0.002*	-0.002*
PaR30	0.036	-0.044	-0.039	-0.095	-0.093	-0.095
Sargan stat.	2.920	3.293	4.352	3.076	2.976	2.305
Sargan p-value	0.40	0.35	0.23	0.38	0.39	0.51
N	377	377	377	406	406	406
R ²	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.17	0.17	0.18
Wald χ^2	116.79***	40.28***	253.88***	270.10***	400.83***	536.08***

Panel B	OSS			FSS		
fraction fem. dir.	0.116			0.694**		
# female directors		-0.005			0.085	
dumfemdir ≥ 3			-0.019			0.391*
lnTA	0.191***	0.191***	0.190***	0.121***	0.107***	0.102***
Age	-0.002	-0.003	-0.001	-0.004	-0.003	-0.005
PaR30	0.341	-0.034	-0.035	-0.549*	-0.521	-0.547
Sargan stat.	5.126	11.170	10.028	1.878	1.592	1.562
Sargan p-value	0.16	0.01	0.02	0.60	0.66	0.67
N	408	408	408	360	360	360
R ²	0.22	0.15	0.11	0.18	0.11	0.11
Wald χ^2	122.12***	199.42***	52.05***	27.11***	37.68***	380.32***

Country control variables: GDPpercapita, Heritage, GDPgrowth

Instruments used

ownership type, internationally initiated, dumrural, gender bias

Table 9. Corporate governance and financial performance. We regress corporate governance on lagged financial performance and controls. Governance is measured through the number of board meetings, a binary for internal audits, and a binary for CEO duality and the number of board members. For the binary governance variables probit regressions are estimated, for the discrete governance variables, tobit-censored regressions are estimated. Significance levels are based on heteroskedastic and autocorrelation-corrected standard errors. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

	<i>Meetings</i>		<i>Internal Audit</i>		<i>CEO Duality</i>		<i>Board size</i>	
lagged financial performance								
ROA t-1	-0.213	-0.549	-0.645	-0.023	-0.163	-0.250	-1.391	-1.912
female leadership								
Female CEO	-1.608***		0.065		0.121		0.694**	
Female chair		-0.775		-0.296**		0.279*		-0.382
MFI controls								
lnTA	1.076***	0.956***	0.344***	0.270***	0.201***	0.242***	0.529***	0.621***
Age	0.219***	0.225***	0.014*	0.023*	-0.032***	-0.039***	-0.011	-0.001
PaR30	0.614	0.751	-0.956	-0.324	-0.258	-0.531	-0.989	-0.352
Competition	-0.007	-0.285	0.071	0.008	-0.055	-0.042	-0.586***	-0.613***
NGO	-0.171	-0.601	-0.681***	-0.823***	0.254*	0.191*	1.880***	2.259***
COOP	6.144***	5.101***	-0.623***	-0.667***	0.495**	0.507***	2.002***	1.604***
country controls								
GDPpercapita	-0.002	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	0.001	0.001	-0.002	-0.001
Heritage	-0.116**	-0.088	-0.002	-0.004	0.042***	0.049***	0.055***	0.053**
GDPgrowth	25.865***	22.055***	2.483	3.761**	-0.601	-1.241	-3.502	-0.102
regional dummies								
	<i>incl.</i>	<i>incl.</i>	<i>incl.</i>	<i>incl.</i>	<i>incl.</i>	<i>incl.</i>	<i>incl.</i>	<i>incl.</i>
N	422	325	615	444	650	587	626	458
F stat. / Wald χ^2	8.78***	9.05***	136.43***	103.29***	51.81***	50.15***	12.19***	9.60***
R ²	0.07	0.06	0.19	0.18	0.10	0.10	0.05	0.05
Method	Tobit	Tobit	Probit	Probit	Probit	Probit	Tobit	Tobit

Table 10: Financial performance when board size and the number of board meetings are included. The Heckman (1979) dummy endogenous model is used in estimations. Significance levels are based on heteroskedastic and autocorrelation-corrected standard errors. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

panel A	ROE			ROA		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
female leadership						
Female CEO	0.198**			0.116*		
Female CHAIR		0.223*			0.088*	
Female DIRECTOR			0.154			0.096*
MFI controls						
lnTA	0.071***	0.078***	0.087***	0.032***	0.027***	0.029***
Age	-0.008*	-0.007*	-0.010*	-0.002*	-0.001	-0.002
par30	-0.267**	-0.339*	-0.585*	-0.075	0.051	0.122
board variables						
board size	0.003	0.007	0.004	-0.002	-0.001	-0.004
# board meetings	0.004	0.003	0.002	0.001	0.001	-0.001
country controls						
GDP per capita	0.001	0.001	0.001	-0.001	0.001	0.001
Heritage	-0.002	-0.003	-0.003	0.001	-0.001	-0.001
GDP growth	0.187	0.028	0.041	0.165	0.152	0.227
regional dummies	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
time dummies	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
model statistics						
N	374	303	246	401	325	260
R ²	0.16	0.12	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.17
Wald χ^2	72.71***	53.47***	51.26***	73.61***	55.54***	39.36***
<i>Instruments: fitted probabilities from a probit explaining binary variables for female CEO, female chair, and female director</i>						

Table 10 continued

panel B	OSS			FSS		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
female leadership						
Female CEO	0.674*			0.578*		
Female CHAIR		0.083			0.383**	
Female DIRECTOR			0.412*			0.091
MFI controls						
lnTA	0.226***	0.237***	0.223***	0.114***	0.121***	0.088***
age	-0.010*	-0.003	-0.007	0.001	-0.001	-0.002
par30	-0.090	0.059	-0.285	-0.625**	-0.857**	-0.782**
board variables						
board size	-0.001	0.019	-0.006	-0.004	0.008	0.006
# board meetings	0.019	0.024	0.028*	0.006	0.001	-0.001
country controls						
GDP per capita	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
Heritage	-0.018*	-0.024*	-0.015*	0.004	-0.004	-0.004
GDP growth	0.223	0.405	0.536	0.806	0.721	0.841
regional dummies	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
time dummies	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
model statistics						
N	403	328	263	317	286	236
R ²	0.23	0.20	0.20	0.16	0.16	0.15
Wald χ^2	116.69***	97.40***	82.39***	56.87***	61.83***	43.51***
<i>Instruments: fitted probabilities from a probit explaining binary variables for female CEO, female chair, and female director</i>						

Appendix A

Countries in the sample and the frequency in each country, and frequency of firms in different world regions

No	Country	Total	No	Country	Total	No	Country	Total
1	Albania	1	31	Moldova	2	61	Chad	1
2	Argentina	1	32	Morocco	4	62	Rwanda	4
3	Armenia	3	33	Nicaragua	9	63	Zambia	1
4	Benin	6	34	Pakistan	1	64	China	1
5	Bolivia	14	35	Paraguay	1	65	Serbia	1
6	Bosnia Hercegovina	10	36	Peru	25	66	Ghana	3
7	Brazil	13	37	Philippines	7	67	Malawi	1
8	Bulgaria	2	38	Romania	1	68	Gambia	1
9	Burkina Faso	3	39	Russian Federation	12	69	Kosovo	4
10	Cambodia	12	40	Senegal	8	70	Rep of CongoBrazz	1
11	Chile	2	41	South Africa	1	71	Burundi	1
12	Colombia	6	42	Sri Lanka	1	72	Niger	1
13	Dominican Republic	3	43	Tanzania	1	73	DRC – Kinshasa	1
14	Ecuador	16	44	Togo	3	Grand Total		329
15	Egypt	4	45	Trinidad and Tobago	1			
16	El Salvador	4	46	Tunisia	1			
17	Ethiopia	7	47	Uganda	5	Regional distribution		
18	Georgia	5	48	Montenegro	2	Code	Region	Total
19	Guatemala	5	49	Cameroun	3	1	Latin America	99
20	Haiti	2	50	Guinee	1	2	Africa	87
21	Honduras	8	51	East Timor	1	3	MENA	33
22	India	30	52	Bangladesh	2	4	EECA	64
23	Indonesia	2	53	Nepal	5	5	Asia	46
24	Jordan	3	54	Vietnam	1	Grand Total		329
25	Kazakhstan	3	55	Azerbaijan	5			
26	Kenya	6	56	Mongolia	2			
27	Kyrgyzstan	3	57	Nigeria	3			
28	Madagascar	1	58	Mozambique	1			
29	Mali	3	59	Tajikistan	4			
30	Mexico	16	60	Croatia	1			

EECA is Eastern Europe and Central Asia; MENA is Middle East and North Africa.